

Artificial Intelligence a threat or a boon to human society? A discussion

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence or AI which has tremendously swept the world with its echeloning efficiency and development is reaching the heights where human creativity is artificially being replaced with profound artificially generated technology. While society has a mechanism or it absorbs different section of people on the basis of their formal education, knowledge and skill the threat remains of replacing human power of creativity/cognition and substituting repetitive task with one button thereby displacing the large quantum of labour force without even realising. The possibilities of AI on the one hand have multifaceted positive side but simultaneously brings uncertainty and ambiguity with potential risk. Increased automation with efficiency leads to ease in tasking but the worth of human being most of who will be unable to match and adapt with it, with less a skill will be reduced not even as a workforce, creating existential threat unable to cope with the innovations of technology.

Keywords: intelligence, technology, automation, innovation, machine, humanity

Introduction:

Profit driven world in which we live where everything is counted on the basis of value it holds in economic terms. Again, world in which we live is unequal in every terms right from skill, knowledge and cognitive powers/capacity to learn new. The probable threat that AI with which we share our life day to day might surpass the natural intelligence of human, intelligence which matches the intelligence of no species in this world till date. The innate human potential to empathize, intuitive power, creativity, spiritual intelligence which is inherently a human trait which can never be emulated will always make a human unparalleled to any other species/being on this planet. If used knowing its limitations AI can improve our lives to the best but the ethical, social and human side of its effects in a long term needs to be taken into consideration.

AI and loss of Human essence

The existing disparity within society in labour market can become more uneven in terms of skilled and unskilled labour force power to cope with the tech-uses and knowledge. In no way should technology be a master of human and if it limits within serving the human concerns than AI can still be regarded as the excellent technological innovation of human so far. The AI enabled future where algorithms and robotics activity may have a chance of effecting every aspect of human life and culture.

Human productivity equals to nothing. The capacity what makes human a different species in this world is their creativity and intelligence. Alongside the values and ethics, the discriminatory power of human between right and wrong, this is all what makes human special. The future we are heading towards may or may not lead to irrelevancy of human existence, but what we regard as social in terms of human interaction has been reduced by non-human centric interaction today. The ambiguity and complexity are what is the essence of being human.” Writes Marina Gorbis:

Artificially intelligent society and disparity

Happiness is what human needs to survive. By freeing human from the mundane and tedious monotony of repetitive task AI can catalyse the possibility of engaging human labour/effort in productive task thus creating contentment. Unlike the Marx idea of alienation aftermath of industrial revolution where human being was reduced to machines delegating work in manufacturing parts of the whole. AI bound future will definitely outperform/is outperforming human performance in any field there by creating a huge gap between again a tech-savvy “haves” and the “have nots”. While the control of most advanced version of AI will always remain with the elite thus accelerating the digital divide in the life of the people. Production of Marx’s concept of alienation may resurface where the increasing loss of agency and autonomy on the part of many to accelerate growth and match the prowess of AI technology might again lead to loss of self-worth and alienation in a new/another sense. These may accelerate disparity among people where most who fail to accommodate with the latest AI tech will feel devalued and thus unworthy in many ways. The relevancy of human power and its erosion with truth being/getting distorted, the discernment of reality will get equally hard.

Materialistic ambition and algorithm driven world

The power of computer excelling human reason will be a definite threat. Driven by materialistic ambition without concerning the humanitarian motives will end up world in an unrealistic array of confusion and unrealistic oblivion. Surrendering the biological intelligence to AI and losing a purpose in life can make human a body without a soul or body devoid of happiness. All dependence on algorithm driven AI leads to uncertainty, unreality and biased society empowering the power mongers. Humankind needs to actively participate in societal activities and development transitioning with the transformation brought about by the technology. The rate and speed of automated tech like AI on the opposite is/will not be comprehensible to all as mentioned creating social disruption and problems.

As known man is a social animal. Human need for community life and social interaction is also equally a necessity that cannot be denied. The rising case of stress and depression among the people today can be possible resultant of the kind of life people are leading and heading towards. With the rise in automated activity human forte to think, to write, creativity, curiosity everything seems to be dying prematurely. The highly automated technology thus impacting the behaviours and psychology of human cannot be avoided rather too much dependence on it is leading towards detachment, disinterested in anything and getting more self-centred, self-oriented, self-focused and self-involved. With diminishing social connections and group life, real life connectivity/experiences, technology mediating and seeping into every aspect of human life, life becomes worthless and dull.

Looming cyber threat

The encroachment of personal security and privacy by the AI driven technology and the continued risk of scamming and fraudulent malpractices continuously looms over creating an awe and alarming situation over time. The spread of malicious content and fake information sometimes can be a cause of societal tensions, conflicts, vulnerabilities of many sorts. Deepfake and highly powered AI technology can have a chance of effecting the loves of people in negative ways thereby raising concerns on cybersecurity.

Human intelligence vis-a vis artificially generated intelligence

AI if used for augmentation of human potential and abilities and for the well-

being of humanity, it will be a boon in disguise. The human-machine/AI if worked in sync will enhance the future of humankind in different level thus creating a different life experience, with fruitful co-existence of both (machine and human). Never ever should technology should be driven just by profit motives, technology if imbued with inclusive, value-based, ethical responsibilities than it can work wonders and can make a world a best place to live. More accessible and available technology to all with socio-political control on its uses can work for general welfare. The core of society is still social control through norms, proper leadership through wisdom which will ensure a better life and world for all. Thus, society's role as a sole one to enforce or impede on use of machine will decide the path it will lead to. Virtual reality in which we have entered stores in itself many possibilities and challenges in itself. While human engagement with machines and machine learning will probably going to increase in the near future, humans face to face interaction, empathy may be reduced. As a human it has to be taken into consideration that we may not evolve into an automated robots with search for increasing perfection and efficiency in our daily life. The humanity has to be kept alive that is what make human unique and that is what constitute humans' strength. Artificial intelligence can in no sense be a match to a human biological/natural intelligence. It is not possible to replicate the consciousness by algorithms, computations, processing, and functions of the AI method. Intelligence is the result of an evolution of the human consciousness by nature and AI cannot follow the path of natural intelligence evolution (Xie, 2021).

Prospect in Collaborative future

Every change impacts us in different way but it definitely comes with a price. AI is transforming our lives, the way we work and the most important of all the patterns of our interaction. Natural inherent potential of human to critically analyse and think will be reduced with algorithmic programming of information. When the usage and dependency of AI are increased, this will automatically limit the human brain's thinking capacity. This, as a result, rapidly decreases the thinking capacity of humans. This removes intelligence capacities from humans and makes them more artificial. In addition, so much interaction with technology has pushed us to think like algorithms without understanding (Sarwat, 2018). Augmentation of automation tasks and amplification of human abilities and insights will discern the new unexplored breakthroughs in world. Informed machine learning and automation can undoubtedly speed up and bring unimaginable changes in the digital landscape. As Nobel Prize winner Joseph Stiglitz said, history demonstrates that "unfettered capitalism, unfettered innovation, does not lead to the general well-being of our society. "The future impact of AI hinges on our ability to harness its potential responsibly, striking a balance between innovations and safeguarding the principles that define a fair, just, and equitable society. (Saksham Mahajan: 2023)

Conclusion

Digital society where we are entering may or may not transform the social fabric, can restructure it in a different path we may not have imagined. Whether it will be a boon or a threat depends on the boundary/limit human will set to the activities AI can perform. Balancing progress and ethics, if used for serving humanity, human and AI can improve our day-to-day life in many ways. Human centric technology and responsible AI can foster our future in new direction. With further evolution of AI based technology, it may affect all aspects of human life thus by being equally vigilant and scrutinizing a risk related to it can be precautious

measures we can take. By fostering transparency, inclusivity, and responsibility in AI development, society can navigate the complexities of this technological revolution, ensuring that AI benefits humanity as a whole. (Pasupuleti, Madurima: 2025)

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